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MCM@towboats: Marine Competitiveness Model applied to Towboats

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Summary

This paper discusses economic, social and environmental challenges of inland navigation (using barges + pusher convoys), faced by main stakeholders of the river systems. After years of analyzing alternative ship designs and operations of this critical marine transportation mode the author has developed an analytical model to measure their competitiveness in useful terms. A simplified version of the MCM@Towboats (Marine Competitiveness Model applied to Towboats) is presented in this paper and competitiveness results are shown for a case study. The Ecopusher® design platform is used for a systemic study of the MCM@t permitting to measure performance improvements of technical-operational solutions in terms of CAPEX and OPEX and also to estimate the harmful atmospheric emissions and social impacts.

Design, Operational and Market Parameters used in the model are discussed as well as those corresponding to emissions and social impacts in terms of jobs, health and availability of public resources.

A case study of a +6000 HP towboat in the Paraguay-Paraná Waterway (PPW) is briefly presented to show the economic, social and environmental impacts of technical solutions and the corresponding performance improvements obtained with respect to conventional pusher designs.

1. Introduction

Inland Waterway Shipping (IWS) is an economic activity that complements other transportation modes as those performed by trains, trucks, and ocean vessels, that conform a multimodal transportation system.

IWS is hard to beat for mid to large volumes (5000 t to 50,000 t) of non-perishable cargo, with source and destination nodes close to a river and separated for mid-long distances (500 km to 5000 km).

Dry bulk cargoes (grains, iron ore, carbon, etc.) or liquid bulk cargoes (oils, fuels, etc.) are the most commonly moved by IWS as the speed of transportation is not as critical as to reach a low economic cost. But for some time now and more and more in the recent years, competitiveness concept is broadening including not only economic aspects but also the environmental and social impacts. Therefore, decision makers are starting to consider also these other “new” aspects in their transportation competitiveness analysis. For instance, cargo-owners following consumer market demand are getting real concern of the carbon footprint of their products and, moving their cargo in a conventionally fueled vessel increases the

footprint, thus decreasing the product value. This is getting a real concern and in the near future will be unacceptable that a ship operator provides a service that reduces the value of its client’s cargo as happens today.

The largest volumes of cargo in IWS are moved most efficiently in non-propelled barges’ convoys (up to 50,000 dwt) pushed by a single powerful towboat (up to 8000 HP) where most of the OPEX, CAPEX and environmental/social impact sources are concentrated.

This new and broader competitiveness concept is generating a new breed of towboats’ designs that could cope with the new market demands and future regulations. The Ecopusher® design platform (protected under Intellectual Property Rights with patent pending) and its tool kit are a response to develop a more competitive towboats’ fleet for the future.

But, in order to decide if it is worth to add a specific improvement in the next towboat, decision makers need to evaluate their cost/benefit ratio.

It is necessary to have quantitative (in addition to qualitative) answers to questions like these:

What is the cost-benefit ratio of:

- using a more planet-friendly fuel?
- using a more people-health-friendly fuel?
- using energy saving devices?
- helping the local communities?

In order to assist in this decision-making analysis of the right design of a new towboat, the author has developed the following MCM@towboats (Marine Competitiveness Model applied to Towboats).

2. MCM@towboats (MCM@t)

As shown in Figure 1, MCM@t has four key parts:

- a series of “built-in” Parameters
- a series of Input Values
- the client set of Criteria
- the Model Output

Figure 1 – MCM@towboat Conceptual Scheme

Built-in MCM parameters are a series of values, formulas and algorithms that allow to produce meaningful results based on a set of inputs values. In order to do this in a systematic form, the Model is based on the Ecopusher® design platform that

includes a tool kit to provide solutions to the clients' needs.

The MCM@t is open to modify parameters as more refined information is gathered and updated data is incorporated, and will also take into account a client specific parameter value or sensibility analysis requirement. There are parameters of very different type as those related to OPEX, CAPEX, Operation, Emissions, Fuel Prices, Carbon Prices, etc.

Input Values are specific of each analysis, based on a type of operation profile and client preferences. These inputs will be typically related to fuel, power, propulsion and steering system preferences, range required, cargo volume, round trip time, special regulations to be considered, crew, draft, dimensions, etc. It is also useful to set the main criteria and weighting factors that will be used to value and compare the resulting alternatives.

Even though there is an initial set of inputs, the iterative process of the MCM@t might propose variations to the initial inputs and offering a trade off or cost/benefit analysis supporting such a modification proposal.

Finally, after a series of discussions with the client the Model Output will be developed in two stages:

- an initial set of two or three alternatives of Ecopusher® designs with their competitiveness results in economic terms as well as considering environmental and social aspects.
- a final proposal of the final design that maximizes competitiveness based on the client's criteria.

In the following chapters will be briefly discussed some of the most relevant aspects of the competitiveness analysis and a will be shared the results of the MCM@t for a specific case in the Paraguay Paraná Waterway (PPW).

The following issues will be presented and the competitiveness impacts will be discussed:

- Energy Efficiency
- Maneuverability Improvements
- Fuel selection
 - o Environmental Impact
 - o Fuel Price Projections
- Minimum Draft

3. Energy Efficiency

Typically, the single most important cost item in inland waterways shipping is related to energy. And there are at least three aspects of the energy on board to be considered:

- How much energy is required?
- How much is the unit energy cost?
- How much is the external cost of energy?

In this chapter will be briefly presented the first aspect, related to the amount of energy required and the other issues will be analyzed later in the following chapters.

Everybody will agree that the most competitive energy is the one that is not used. The unused energy is cheap (zero cost) and generates no atmospheric damage (zero emissions). But without energy the cargo will not be moved then, the most we can do is to minimize the amount of energy required and to do that it is wise to copy a great energy saver: Nature.

As an example of how naval architects copy nature to save energy on board, we will refer to a very efficient swimmer: the penguin.

As shown in Figure 2, penguins minimize friction and resistance by optimizing water flow, avoiding disturbance appendices and creating an air lubrication layer around their bodies.

Figure 2 – Ship Energy Saving inspired on penguins

The micro-air-bubbles layers as energy saving systems are already been used in large ocean-going vessels and its application to barges is very promising as the maximum effects is obtained combining a large surface area (convoy is 290m x 64m) with a low speed (convoy speed is usually under 14 km-h).

Inspired in Nature, the Ecopusher® tool kit offers three energy saving improvements that can reach 22,6% energy savings with respect to conventional designs by removing flanking rudders, improving hydrodynamics and using high performance propellers and steering systems.

For example, in a 6000 HP pusher diesel-fueled, consuming 3000 m³ of diesel per year at an average cost of 800 usd/m³ on the PPW, the economic impact of implementing these energy saving improvements would be over 0,5 million USD per year (0,5 MMUSD/y).

Even much higher energy savings values (up to over 37%) could be achieved by using a hybrid full gas + electric + batteries propulsion system but this option would require a significantly higher initial CAPEX.

From the environmental and social points of view the energy saving would be a large reduction of harmful emission both for the planet and the local community's health.

Energy efficiency performance is monitored over time with the Digitwins® digital twins technology to have real time information of key performance parameters and to anticipate any problems or to solve any operational errors.

4. Maneuverability Improvement

A fairly large amount of round-trip time is lost in the maneuvering operations over the numerous river-bends typical of river systems with large and fully loaded convoys (over 40,000 dwt, 290 m long x 64 m wide).

Therefore, by improving the steering capabilities of the pusher (by avoiding the flanking operation, among others measures) this maneuvering time can be reduced with multiple positive effects.

A simulation performed by Consulmar pusher design team at the USP Numerical Testing Tank proved that, replacing flanking rudders by high performance main rudders, the maneuvering time could be drastically reduced (30 minutes/bend), permitting to make more round trips/year.

Applying those results in the MCM@t are obtained the following results:

- Important energy savings, already included in previous analysis.
- Fleet CAPEX reductions.
- Financial Cost reductions.
- Extra Operating Margin.

The improvement in maneuverability has a very high impact in the full convoy investment. The reason is that, by reducing the maneuvering time at the many river bends, it can be reduced the roundtrip duration. This allows to move more cargo

per year generating more revenue or, seeing it from another side, it permits to move the same amount of annual cargo with a smaller number of convoys. This means that it is possible to make the same business with a smaller fleet, getting a higher profitability over the invested CAPEX.

Using MCM@t the following economic impacts are calculated: as in the PPW there are over 164 river bends, 3.4 days could be saved per full round trip (RT). This is a 10% reduction in the typical RT time of 34 days in a modern equivalent conventional pusher and the economic impacts are:

- 3,9 MMUSD saving in fleet CAPEX to move the same annual cargo volume: 10% of 39 MMUSD (16 barges + pusher CAPEX).
- 0,30 MMUSD/yr saving in CAPEX financial cost (3,9 MMUSD @ 8%, 40yrs).
- 0,36 MMUSD/yr extra Operating Margin: 10% x 36,000 t/RT x 9 RT/yr x 11 USD/t (unit op. margin).

MCM@t shows that basic energy savings measures and maneuverability improvements applied to the Ecopusher® require minimum extra CAPEX with respect to conventional pushers and has a low payback period of only 1 year.

5. Fuel

Probably the larger present impact in ship design is the change from the conventional diesel oil or fuel oil to a more environmentally friendly alternative like LNG/LPG (fossil or bio), Ethanol or Green Hydrogen carriers like Methanol or Ammonia. But there are also other even more disrupting options as those that do not even need internal combustion engines as are the solutions based on chemistry instead of mechanics like fuel cells or electric batteries. Many ship operators are already considering these greener options as a way to comply with existing and/or future regulations.

In the decision-making process of selecting a marine fuel for a new vessel there are multiple barriers/uncertainties to overcome. Some of them are listed below and briefly discussed as follows (15):

- Technical maturity of main equipment.
- Fuel availability and infrastructure.
- Present and projected future fuel price.
- Rules and Regulations.
- Extra CAPEX respect to DO/FO.
- Volumetric Energy Density.

Figure 3 – Alternative New Fuel Barriers (15)

From this analysis and many others, LNG appears as clear winner as marine transition fuel, but among these variables, the uncertainty of an efficient bunkering service is probably the major barrier of adoption of a new fuel. This is clearly explained by the Chicken & Egg Dilemma: no ship operator will order a new vessel powered by a fuel that is not available in the ports of call. And on the other side of the coin, no energy company will produce a marine fuel that no vessel demands.

Figure 4 – Chicken and Egg Dilemma

It took some time, but finally it was solved successfully and LNG is widely available as marine transition fuel at many ports worldwide (16).

- There are some 200 ports bunkering LNG.
- 80 additional ports are getting ready to bunker LNG in the near future.
- There over 60 vessels offering ship to ship bunkering services.
- In 2024, Singapore has delivered 340,000t LNG and Rotterdam has increased its output 44% with respect to 2023, reaching 300,000t LNG in 2024.

Figures 5 summarizes a comparative analysis of marine fuels recently (2025) developed by the MCM@t for a major river operator in the PPW in early 2025

Six alternative fuels versus twelve criteria are presented in a summary matrix where darker cells show the least convenient fuel for each criterion. In this case, the LNG / BioLNG combination appears as the best fuel solutions for the region (most of the light-colored cells correspond to these two greener fuels).

CRITERIA	FUEL ALTERNATIVES CONSIDERED FOR NEW PPW PUSHERS					
	MGO	IFO	BIO-ETHANOL	LNG	BIO-LNG	E-METHANOL
ACTUAL PRICE	HIGH	HIGH	HIGH	VERY LOW	VERY LOW	VERY HIGH
FUTURE PRICE	HIGHER		SIMILAR	SIMILAR	MUCH LOWER	
\$\$ STABILITY	UNSTABLE		STABLE	SEMI STABLE	STABLE	
GREEN FINANCE	NO ACCESS		LIMITED	FULL ACCESS		
CAPEX	VERY LOW	LOW	MEDIUM	MEDIUM HIGH	VERY HIGH	
EMISSIONS	VERY HIGH		LOW	ZERO		
CO2 FOOTPRINT	VERY HIGH		LOW	HIGH	ZERO	
SPILL DAMAGE	VERY HIGH		VERY LOW			
REGULATIONS	VERY NEGATIVE		QUITE GOOD	VERY POSITIVE		
AVAILABILITY	VERY EASY		QUITE EASY	EASY AND CHEAP TO DEVELOP	NOT YET	
HANDLE-STORE	VERY EASY	INTERM.	CRYOGENIC TEMPERATURE		INTERM.	
SHIP DESIGN	VERY EASY	EASY	EXTRA FUEL STORAGE CAP. AND NEW FUEL SYSTEMS NEEDED			

Figure 5 – PPW Alternative Fuels versus Criteria Matrix

Figure 6 presents the twelve criteria divided in three groups as they relate to Economic, Environmental or Operational issues.

FUEL COMPARISON CRITERIA	
In order to compare the fuel alternatives at PPW different criteria are proposed for consideration. Some of them are here presented, divided in 3 main groups: Economical, Environmental and Operational	
Economical criteria	
ACTUAL COST:	Takes into account present Production, Transportation and Bunkering service.
PROJECTED COST:	It considers market trends, based on availability, carbon economy and other factors.
PRICE STABILITY:	It addresses the problem of instability of fuel price due to external factors.
FINANCING:	It considers that certain environmental friendly fuels give access to subsidized green finance.
CAPEX:	Takes into account the differences in CAPEX for different marine fuels.
Environmental criteria	
HARMFUL EMISSIONS:	Considers SOx, NOx and PM local impact harmful emissions and global impact of CO ₂ .
CARBON FOOTPRINT:	It addresses the impact of a new value of cargo: the carbon footprint marked by the fuel.
FUEL SPILL DAMAGE:	Takes into account the damage to river species and humans due to fuel spills.
REGULATIONS:	It considers present and future regulations affecting PPW transportation.
Operational criteria	
BUNKERING AVAILABILITY:	It considers the certainty of fuel availability at the PPW ports of call.
HANDLING & STORING:	Takes into account special requirements: temperature, toxicity, special training, etc.
SHIP DESIGN:	It addresses design aspects as Fuel Energy Density, Range and Fuel flexibility w/minimum impact.

Figure 6 – Set of criteria for the MCM agreed w/ client

Regional PPW production paths are presented in the next figure showing that the six considered fuels can be produced efficiently in the region but the only one that is available for all the five PPW countries is the bioLNG as its competitiveness is based in the abundant and low-cost biomass available in the region.

Figure 7 – PPW alternative marine fuel pathways

In order to make an even more complete comparison LPG/bioLPG should also be included as will be the case in a future version of this study that is in progress.

In the MCM@t there are two critical aspects in the fuel selection:

- Environmental (emissions) Impact.
- Projected Fuel Price.

The following two subchapters address these two key aspects of the fuel selection at the MCM@t.

5.1. Environmental Impact of Fuel

Studies conducted by the Institute of Atmospheric Physics of the German Aerospace Centre (DLR) and the College of Marine and Earth Studies of the University of Delaware, USA, conclude that ship emissions are responsible for 2.7% of all human-caused CO₂ emissions.

The definitions and regulations of international organizations are compelling.

“If we fail to reduce polluting emissions from the maritime industry, we are heading for an environmental disaster.”

Isabelle Durant, Deputy Director of the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development, Global Maritime Forum, Singapore.

“Current levels of emissions from shipping are unacceptable [...]. The shipping industry needs a new revolution in its propulsion systems.”

Lee Adamson, International Maritime Organization (IMO).

Whether due to regulatory obligations or due to business conscience, shipowners have long since begun to look for solutions to reduce emissions.

The most immediate alternative was to use more expensive refined fossil fuels that complied with emissions regulations. In addition to being costly and having a partial impact, this solution generates another negative environmental impact, since the production of these less harmful fossil fuels entails higher CO₂ emissions in the refinery process.

Another option was the installation of large scrubbers to reduce emissions in the exhaust gas system. This is another partial solution that requires a relatively low initial investment but higher operating costs.

Many of these solutions might work in the short term, but in the medium term, they are not sufficient, so alternatives have emerged that contribute to this goal using fuels that are much more environmentally and health-friendly, without increasing operating costs. One of them is the use of Liquefied Natural Gas (LNG) as a cheaper and cleaner fuel, considered a transition to BioLNG, which can achieve complete CO₂ elimination.

The environmental and health damage caused by harmful emissions from ships in general depends on three factors: proximity to the population, type of fuel used, and volume consumed.

- The proximity of the polluting vessel to cities is critical, especially for the health of the most vulnerable populations (children and the elderly). For this reason, there are Emission Control Zones

(ECAs) that seek to protect coastal populations by requiring the use of fuels (or systems) that are increasingly less harmful to health.

- The type of fuel consumed will cause different emission levels. Fuel oil is more polluting than diesel oil, which in turn is much more polluting than LNG, which in turn emits more CO₂ than bioLNG or H₂Green-based fuels.

- The volume of harmful emissions generated by ships is proportional to the volume of fuel consumed. For this reason, among the main challenges is reducing fuel consumption through hydrodynamic optimization of vessels, their propulsion systems, and other methods such as air bubbles lubrication, speed reduction, and smarter operational decisions.

Harmful emissions can be divided into two groups based on the type and reach of damage caused:

- Global, planetarium reach.
- Local, domestic reach.

CO₂ emissions have global impact, generating green-house-gases (GHG) that cause climate change, affecting the planet and putting future generations at risk.

The other main air pollutants (SO_x, NO_x, and PM₁₀) have a more domestic impact as they affect the health of coastal populations near ship operations, causing skin diseases and cardiovascular and respiratory problems (lung cancer).

The following image provides a simplified comparison of some of the main fuels according to their level of harmful emissions relative to the harmful emissions generated by ships fueled with MGO/IFO.

Figure 8 – Harmful emissions simplified comparison

To conduct a more detailed study of the CO₂ emissions of alternative fuels studied throughout their life cycles, MCM@t has incorporated studies

from seven references, yielding the results summarized in the following table.

Ref	IFO	MGO	Fossil MET	LNG	BioLNG	BioMET	BioE-MET	E-MET	BioEthanol
1	97	95	91	70	55	5	2	1	35
2	93	75	83	61					
3	87	87	93	58+5	0+20	0+7			
4			90	90	25				
5									21
6									33
7a									12
7b									42

Adopted Value	89	65	0	0	0	0	0	29	
Avoided gCO ₂ /MJ	0%	0%	0%	-27%	-100%	-100%	-100%	-100%	-68%
gCO ₂ /MJ	0	0	0	-24	-89	-89	-89	-89	-60
ICCO ₂ /GJ	0	0	0	-0,024	-0,089	-0,089	-0,089	-0,089	-0,0604

Figure 9 – Life Cycle Emissions comparison Table

Next figure presents the life cycle emissions in a graphical manner using as a base the graph and data of the mentioned reference.

Figure 10 – Life Cycle Emissions comparison Graph

By mixing LNG + BioLNG it is possible to reach zero emissions as BioLNG can have high levels of GHG reduction (-188% DO) using cow manure and considering emissions avoidance as shown in Figure 11 (ref.4).

Figure 11 – GHG emissions change comparison % (4)

According to a European Commission study published in early 2005, the presence of Particulate Matter (PM₁₀), such as soot and ash emitted from ship chimneys, causes 288,000 premature deaths each year. The World Health Organization (WHO) study, published a study in 2004, that explains that

exposure to these suspended particles is the cause of the premature deaths of 13,000 children between the ages of one and four each year. The study (8) conducted by scientists from the University of Delaware and the Rochester Institute of Technology (RIT) for the American Chemical Society shows the number of premature deaths attributable to Particulate Matter (PM) from ship combustion emissions in the most affected areas of the planet.

Figure 12 – Ship Emissions Mortality Impact (8)

Based on these studies, MCM@t is able to estimate the social impact in terms of premature deaths avoided by selecting a greener marine fuel.

In a just society, every crime is punished proportionally, usually with an economic value related to the cost of the damage caused. Something similar should occur with pollution, understood as environmental social damage. In Europe, where awareness of this issue is high and growing, there are economic penalty systems for pollution. In our region environmental damage goes unpunished and therefore its harder to make the change in the right direction.

Harmful emissions from ships cause damage whose social costs are not considered by governments, much less by shipowners; these ones are referred as "external cost" to differentiate them from the "internal" costs (fuel, personnel, repairs, etc.), which shipowners are aware of and try to minimize because a price has to be paid.

The environmental costs of ship emissions seem hidden but are very real as they impact the public health budget, among other aspects. Emissions are generated free of charge by the ship operators, but are unfairly paid by the polluted population. This represents a subsidy that incentivizes continued pollution for free. In Europe, however, a fairer policy is already beginning to be applied, summed up in the phrase: *whoever does it, pays for it*. This process seeks to "internalize" external costs; that is, to have shipowners bear the cost of the damage through higher taxes on polluting fuels, leading to investing in more environmentally friendly ships.

Another aspect that seems more distant, but is equally important, is the valuation of the "planetary

external cost," that is, the cost related to Climate Change, which affects all of humanity (current and, above all, future) due to global warming generated by greenhouse gases, the main representative of which is CO₂.

The following graph, adapted from reference (9) shows the projected external cost caused by CO₂ (Euros/tonne-CO₂). In the center, between the two most likely scenario curves and for the period (2022-2037), is the average value of 80 Euros/tonne-CO₂ which, when extrapolated is almost the same carbon price (100 usd/tCO₂) recently set by IMO as a minimum charge to ships' emissions from 2028 on.

Figure 13 – Carbon Price projection (9)

The MCM@t demonstrates that a 6000 HP conventional diesel-fueled towboat operating along the PPW year around, generates some 10,000 tCO₂/year. Therefore, with a net zero Ecopusher® running on a mix of LNG+BioLNG it can be generated 1 MMusd/yr of extra revenue from Carbon Credits, reducing environmental impact.

Another way to economically value this planetary damage caused by CO₂ emissions is found in the very recent "carbon market," which is an indicator of the price paid by companies that emit CO₂ to those with negative CO₂ activities. This is a new type of market that "compensates" projects that make the greatest effort to protect the planet through the purchase and sale of carbon credits.

One of the greatest current challenges facing humanity is achieving the decarbonization of the economy. In this case, we are referring to the contribution we can make through river and maritime transport to the global effort to reduce the impact of climate change.

This requires a transition from the current polluting fossil fuels used in navigation, such as the various forms of Fuel Oil (FO) and Diesel Oil (DO), to other clean energy systems.

These fossil fuels currently used in vessels generate harmful emissions that harm the environment and

health, causing illness and death in the communities closest to them.

Societies are increasingly beginning to recognize this problem and are therefore demanding effective controls and regulations from their governments, who, on the other hand, are under strong pressure from economic lobbies seeking to maintain the polluting status quo to avoid (or at least delay) the corresponding investments.

5.2. Projected Fuel Prices

This section discusses Fuel Cost Projections in the PPW in terms of energy equivalency (usd/MMBTU) in order to make all alternatives comparable.

The six fuel alternatives available at the PPW considered in the MCM@t are MGO, IFO, Fossil METHANOL, LNG, Bio LNG and Bio Ethanol. They are valued in USD₂₀₂₄ to be considered for 2025. LPG is also available in the PPW but its inclusion is still under analysis.

The other three fuels also considered in the MCM@t are Bio METHanol, Bio E-MET and E-MET and are also valued in USD₂₀₂₄, but for 2028 when they might be available. All nine fuels values are projected for year 2040.

The four fuels with fossil origin (MGO, IFO, Fossil MET and LNG) are projected with a slight cost increment considering the effect of carbon economy.

The fuels with green H₂ origin are projected with a rapid cost decrease as the technology matures, volume increase and production costs are drastically reduced, expecting to reach close to 17 usd/MMBTU by 2040.

LNG and Bio LNG are the lowest cost alternatives during the whole period, but for the future, probably Green Methanol fuels (E-MET and/or BioE-MET) are the most promising ones.

The analysis presented here also considers the impact of a range of projected economic value of the CO₂ avoided.

It follows a brief presentation of each fuel cost projection, identifying the source of the information and the need of further research.

LNG & BIO LNG

The values for Liquefied Natural Gas (LNG) and Bio LNG are based on estimates of current private projects where the author is involved in the PPW area. These fuel production projects are based on the minimum economical sized scalable plant to be built with an output capacity of 309,000 MMBTU/yr (1 x 750 kgLNG/h).

CAPEX is higher for bioGNL as biogas has to be produced while the natural gas is obtained directly from the gas line. Also, biogas from corn forage

needs a larger investment than from cow manure as its energy density is lower. This is also clear in the parameter of CAPEX (usd/MMBTU-yr) that is 60 to 70 for the Bio LNG production and only 39 for the LNG production.

The annual impact of CAPEX is calculated considering 25 years period and an interest rate of 14% to take into account a profit over the capital.

OPEX (usd/MMBTU) varies on the cost of the biomass or the natural gas, considered at extreme reasonable market values in Argentina 2024. The OPEX also takes into account the production costs and the logistics up to the plant and up to the port. Considering CAPEX amortization cost converted in usd/MMBTU, is obtained a final value range of 16,5 to 25 usd/MMBTU for Bio LNG and 10,7 to 15,7 usd/MMBTU for LNG.

The 2025 and 2028 value for BioLNG is 16,5 usd/MMBTU as there is enough cheap cow manure in the area to be used. For 2040 it is considered that 10% of biomass will be corn forage.

For LNG, initial 2025 value is 10,7 usd/MMBTU and is projected a 0,8% annual increase.

Bio MET, E-MET and Bio E-MET

For Methanol obtained from biogas (Bio MET) and Methanol obtained from green H₂ (E-MET) the minimum plant size is considered to have 1,300,000 MMBTU/yr capacity. For Bio E-MET, the minimum plant is twice that size.

It is not foreseen that these fuels would be produced in the PPW area any earlier than by 2028. The economics of these three green fuels are considered separately, as follows:

Bio MET source is biogas obtained 50% from cow manures and 50% from corn forage, and to produce it a 38,6 MMusd CAPEX is required. To convert biogas into BioMET is required an extra investment of 48 MMusd. Adding other necessary investments, the minimum total CAPEX would be in the order of 98 MMusd (75,5 usd/MMBTU-yr).

In the three cases the annual impact of CAPEX is calculated considering 25 years period and an interest rate of 14% including a profit over the invested capital. For the OPEX is taken the average value of 4,7 usd/MMBTU averaging costly forage and free manure. It is added the estimated methanol production and logistics cost of 3,9 usd/MMBTU and a CAPEX impact of 11 usd/MMBTU. It is estimated that this fuel might be available by 2028 at a value of 19,6 usd/MMBTU.

E-MET is obtained from green Hydrogen and CO₂. The basic formula is $(200 \text{ KgH}_2 + 1,4 \text{ tCO}_2) / \text{tMET}$.

The CAPEX to produce the required volume of green H₂ is 121 MMusd and for the Methanol plant is 48 MMusd. With the other investment it adds up to 181 MMusd or 138 usd/MMBTU-yr.

For the OPEX, are considered: 2,7 usd/kg H₂ (using Itaipú hydroelectricity and including CAPEX amortization), and 60 usd/tCO₂ getting it from local industries. Adding other costs and annual CAPEX amortization it is obtained a final 2028 estimated value of 39,9 usd/MMBTU.

Bio E-MET is obtained by combining BioMET and E-MET, getting more volume at an intermediate cost. In this case it is considered a 50/50 combination and it is assumed that total CAPEX is the combination of the CAPEX required for BioMET and for E-MET plants. Therefore, would be required a total CAPEX of 279 MMUSD to produce 2,600,000 MMBTU/yr resulting in 107 usd/MMBTU-yr.

Given a combination factor of 50/50, the expected OPEX is the average of BioMET and E-MET Opex, resulting in an estimated value 2028 of 29,7 usd/MMBTU

These three green methanol alternatives are expected to reduce their costs by 2040, reaching the following estimated values: Bio MET: 18 usd/MMBTU; Bio E- MET: 17 usd/MMBTU; and E-MET: 16,5 usd/MMBTU

Bio ETHANOL

The market values for Bio Ethanol obtained from corn or sugar cane in Brazil are taken from CEPEA-ESALQ-USP web page (10), as referenced in (12). The following graph shows the market value evolution for the last 22 years (2002-2024). The series average value, coincident with 2024 value, is 447 usd/m³ = 22,2 usd/MMBTU (@ 20,1 MMBTU/m³ ethanol) without considering transportation cost to the port.

Figure 14 – Bio Ethanol Prices (12)

To consider transportation cost of ethanol up to a port in the PPW it was found that the closest ethanol production plant in Brazil is in Dourados, 570 km away from Corumbá and Asunción, adding an extra cost of 2,85 usd/MMBTU (@ 0,005 usd/MMBTU-km).

The following map (11) locates the 20 ethanol plants in Brazil, indicating whether they are full corn or corn + sugar cane.

Figure 15 – Ethanol Plants location in Brazil (11)

Therefore, the Brazilian ethanol at a PPW port would have a cost of 25,1 usd/MMBTU. The series trend of 2% p.a is coincident with the projection at 't Hart ref. (7). Bio Ethanol does not look very convenient for new constructions as it is too costly and the CO₂ abatement impact is not that high.

Fossil METHANOL

The initial range of values for fossil methanol (10 to 20 usd / MMBTU) obtained from natural gas (Fossil MET) is taken from IRENA Met reference (14). Assuming that the closest Methanol plant to a PPW port is 250 km away, an extra transportation cost of 1,25 usd/MMBTU is added (0,005 usd/MMBTU-km). Therefore, the range is 11,25 to 21,25 usd/MMBTU and the average value considered for 2025 is 16,3 usd/MMBTU.

In the projections, a 0,8% p.a cost increase is considered due to the carbon economy impact over natural gas derived fuels.

The following graph (Figure 16), modified from the one on IRENA Met reference (14), shows the international ranges of Fossil Met, E-MET and BioMET, as well as their estimated values for PPW by 2025. It confirms the local competitiveness of BioMET and E-MET, with respect to global markets. Fossil MET is not used in the PPW because no vessel is prepared for methanol and it is not offered as marine fuel. The main advantages to consider it for a new construction is the lower fuel cost and to have a vessel ready to accept the even more competitive green methanol in the future.

Figure 16 – Methanol Prices comparison (16)

MGO and IFO

Marine Gas Oil (MGO) and Intermediate Fuel Oil (IFO) are the only fuels currently used in the PPW. Their prices vary in a very wide range depending on external factors out of local stakeholder's control. The data source is the market price paid by major operators in the PPW during 5 years (2018-2023).

Figure 17 – MGO and FO price history in PPW

The result of the analysis are the following values: MGO: 20,6 usd/MMBTU and IFO: 16,7 usd/MMBTU. In the projections, a 1% p.a cost increase is considered due to the carbon economy impact over these fossil fuels. It is interesting to see that MGO at Asunción ports is 5% more expensive than at Argentine ports (Rosario area) and following the same logic, its price in Corumbá area would be an extra 5% higher. All these prices do not include taxes but include transportation cost to the PPW port.

The main drivers to keep using these fuels in the PPW are the following:

- they are available in all ports.
- no extra CAPEX is required to keep the operation as is.
- the vessels have been designed to use them.
- the crews are used to handle them.
- there is no regulation to force a change, nor incentive scheme to promote it.
- there is no real incentive of cargo owners to reduce their goods footprint.
- there is no other fuel available in the PPW ports.
- all the vessels use them.
- ship operators are very conservative, fairly short minded and not too conscious of the harm these fuels cause to their crews, the coastal population and the planet.

The main problems to keep using them are the following:

- they generate large amounts of harmful emissions.
- they are more expensive than other alternatives.
- their price is out of ship operator's control.
- they are stolen from the vessels (10%) generating a criminal climate on board.

This last problem (fuel robbery) is considered an important social impact issue in the MCM@t because, on-board robbery affects crew and company culture and is the entrance gate to much worse crimes as smuggling, drug trafficking and white-slave traffic.

FUEL PRICE CONCLUSIONS

Figure 18 summarizes the PPW cost projections built in the MCM@t for the nine fuels considered up to year 2040 but adjustments are made periodically in order to have the model as updated as possible.

The first set of values assume that avoided CO₂ emissions have no market value (0 usd/tCO₂). In the second set, values of carbon avoidance are considered at very conservative prices (20 to 70 usd/tCO₂).

As for each fuel has been estimated the CO₂ avoidance capacity (tCO₂/MMBTU) the corresponding credit is discounted in each case.

Figure 18 – Fuel Price projection at PPW

In the following graphs (Figure 19) are shown the projections for 0 usd/tCO₂, concluding that, in that scenario at the PPW the most economical fuel is and will be LNG for many years.

BioLNG is also a very competitive fuel for the long term but, at 0 usd/tCO₂ there will be little interest to fuel vessels in a more environmentally friendly way.

This is good demonstration of the importance of economic incentives to decarbonize the shipping activity as the new IMO regulations will impact generating a carbon credits market

Figure 19 – Prices Projection at PPW @ 0 usd/tCO₂

The saving for a 6000 HP pusher in the PPW that requires 3000 m³DO/year would be:

- 2,4 MMusd/yr is the Fuel Cost with DO: 3000m³/yr x 800 usd/m³DO
- 1,3 MMusd/yr is the Cost w/LNG+bioLNG 3000 m³DO x 36,3 MMBTU/m³DO x 11,5 usd/MMBTU (avg yrs. 2028-2040)
- 1,1 MMusd/yr is the Annual Fuel Saving

In addition to the lowest cost there is another important benefit of LNG. Based on the Argentine natural gas price system it is possible to get a long-term fixed LNG price versus the high unpredictable volatility of MGO/IFO prices, governed by external factors totally out of control by ship operators. Figure 20 presents the same type of data but for the bottom part of the table presented in Figure 18. In this case the carbon price is considered to be 20 usd/tCO₂ by 2025, with a slight increase up to 25 usd/tCO₂ by 2028 and finally to reach 70 usd/tCO₂ by 2040.

Figure 20– Prices Projection at PPW @20-70 usd/tCO₂

In this scenario, MCM@t shows that LNG+BioLNG is the most convenient fuel option, but by 2040, other green fuels, based on Green Hydrogen will also be very competitive. The nicety of this analysis is that it is able to combine economic and environmental considerations in the same result.

Taking this last (most realistic, even though conservative) scenario, MCM@t calculates the potential economic saving for a 6000 HP pusher in the PPW that requires 3000 m³DO/year with a conventional towboat design:

- 2,4 MMusd/yr is the Fuel Cost with DO: 3000m³/yr x 800 usd/m³DO
- 1,3 MMusd/yr is the Cost w/LNG+bioLNG 3000 m³DO x 36,3 MMBTU/m³DO x 11,5 usd/MMBTU mix (LNG+bioLNG)
- 1,1 MMusd/yr is the Annual Fuel Saving

6. Minimum Draft

Climate Change is affecting very seriously the inland waterways navigation reducing the available draft. In the Paraguay-Paraná Waterway (PPW) extreme droughts are more frequent and last longer. Last decade is a clear example of the new trend that is not going to change; on the contrary, the lack of strength in global environment protection actions is worsening the situation.

The immediate reaction of the river operators is to increase the river dredging efforts, focusing in the critical points of the river. But additional dredging has an economical and physical limit and also affects the environment. Therefore, it makes a lot of sense to reduce the operational minimum draft of the high-powered pushers reaching a real 5'-6" ultra-low draft, as is attained with the Ecopusher® with over 6000 HP.

In order to evaluate the benefit of reducing draft, the MCM@t has recently delivered the following analysis for a regional river operator.

Based on the projection of the statistical data of PPW river levels, by reducing towboat draft to 5'-6" the new ultra-low draft convoy will be the only one able to operate in a portion of an average year, getting up to 1,5 extra RT with respect to normal 6' low draft pushers. It is obvious that convoy cargo capacity is reduced to 22,000 dwt, but freight value increases compensating for the lower dwt, yielding a unit margin of 14 usd/t. Therefore, MCM@t predicts that at 5'-6" there is an extra annual Operating Margin of:

- 0,46 MMUSD/yr extra Operating Margin: 22,000 t/RT x 1,5 RT/yr x 14 usd/t (unit op. margin)

With the right ship design, the extra CAPEX can be reduced up to a level that is paid back in the first year of extreme low draft, with the additional benefit of being the only convoy able to guarantee the service at such low river levels.

Having this ultra-low draft designs in the market; cargo owners will never again accept so easily the conventional excuse of "lack of water/rain" for a river transportation service breakdown.

Up to now they only had the chance to pray for enough rain/river level to meet their international contracts. But with an ultra-low draft Ecopusher® CEOs of cargo or shipping corporations will not have to rely on "dance rain" anymore.

Figure 21 – CEOs dancing for rain to move cargo

7. Case Study Competitiveness Summary

During the different chapters of this paper, were presented partial results of the competitiveness of specific improvements applied to an Ecopusher® of over 6000 HP operating with 40,000 dwt convoys (4x4 barges) all along the PPW with enough range to do only one bunkering operation per RT. This case was studied for a major river operator in the PPW and the economic impacts (already detailed) resulting from the MCM@t can be summarized as follows:

- MMUSD/yr
- 0,50 saved in Energy Efficiency
- 0,30 saved in Fleet CAPEX financial cost
- 0,36 extra Margin (Maneuvering/RT)
- 1,10 saved in Fuel Cost
- 0,46 extra Margin (Ultra Low Draft)
-
- 2,72 MMUSD/yr benefit
- 1,00 extra Margin w/CC (Carbon Credits)
-
- 3,72 MMUSD/yr benefit w/ CC

Considering that a conventional modern pusher DO/IFO-fueled pusher of 6000HP costs 15 MMUSD/u in the regional market delivered at the PPW, the extra CAPEX required for this Highly Efficient, Ultra Low Draft, Zero Emission, High Range +6000 HP new pusher would be paid back in less than 2 years of operation with the above calculated extra benefits.

The Ecopusher® has been designed to facilitate the modular construction and to maximize the local content. Designing and building in the region, over 60% of local content can be reached keeping a very competitive cost and minimum delivery terms.

Taking a parameter of 21 jobs/MMUSD (17), the MCM@t estimates the 400 jobs are generated per pusher locally built, and considering that in the South American river systems over 200 high power

pushers will be needed in the next two decades, the social impact in terms of job generation becomes very important.

On top of that, there are additional benefits as the followings:

- 3,9 MMUSD total Convoy CAPEX reduction
- Over 60% local content
- Interest rate reduction for Green Ship Loan
- No Risk of fuel spill environmental damage
- Future ready to technology/fuel changes
- Future ready to comply Environment Rules
- Impact of stopping crime culture on board

8. Final Conclusion

In the decision-making process of the new construction or transformation of a towboat there are too many alternatives to choose from. Many of them relate to the ship design itself but many others to operational aspects and they can all be analyzed under three competitiveness criteria: environment, economic and social impact. But this analysis is neither easy nor straight forward and the final decision will be strongly dependent on the relative weights of each criterion. These weighting factors differ from one decision maker to another and due to personal / corporate preferences and external factors. The decisions have to be taken, and as they have large investment and future costs impacts, they should be based on thorough analysis and proven methodologies.

MCM@t can be a useful tool to help in this critical decision-making process taking into account many improvement measures at the same time with the ability to analyze independently their cost saving impact and pay back periods. With the MCM@t it is possible also to make sensibility analysis.

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